

**REPORT ON THE DEPLOMENT PLANS AND ASSEMBLING FOR THE GEN3
WIMEA-ICT AUTOMATIC WEATHER STATION PROTOTYP**

(21st - 23rd February 2018 and 30th – 3rd August 2018)

**Workstation: WIMEA-ICT Lab, Block B, College of Computing and Information Sciences,
Makerere University**

**UNIVERSITY
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Acronyms

AWS	Automatic Weather Station
RSS2 Node	Radio Sensor Node
WIMEA-ICT	Improving Weather Information Management in East Africa for effective service provision through suitable ICTs.
UNMA	Uganda National Meteorological Authority
TMA	Tanzania Meteorological Authority
UoJ	University of Juba

1. Introduction

The WIMEA-ICT project[1] assembled Generation (Gen 3) Automatic Weather (AWS) stations between 21st - 23rd February 2018 and 30th – 3rd August 2018. The aim of the assembly was to gather components, forming 25 AWSs to be installed in Tanzania, Uganda and South Sudan, under batch 1. The 25 AWSs, forming the first batch/batch 1 of the 70 AWSs, which were to be installed in the three countries by the end of the project. The assembly process was done by the Research Component 3¹ PhD students, 12 interns and supervised by the project Principal Investigator and in line with the initial assumptions [2] and as per the changes proposed in the project experimental results.

Each AWS was planned to be assembled and composed of the following 4 components. Each node's component was to be enclosed in a box.

Table 1. Components considered to complete a single AWS.

Item	10m node	2m node	Grd node	Sink node+ gateway	Total
RSS2 Sensor node	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
0.5 W Solar panels	✓	✓	✓		75
2000 Ah battery				✓	25
270F LIC	✓	✓	✓		75
2W Solar panel				✓	25
3400 Ah Battery	✓				25
Anemometer	✓				25
Boost Converter	✓	✓	✓		75
Box	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Electron 3G cellular board				✓	17
MCP3422 ADC card	✓				25
PM5611 Pressure sensor			✓		25
Radiation Shield		✓			25
Rain Gauge			✓		25

¹ The component under WIMEA-ICT, a NORAD project whose role is providing innovative solutions and re-contextualizing several technologies in the AWS ecosystem ranging from wireless sensor networks, up-link options and power system design and maintenance in order to increase the density of AWSs in Uganda, Tanzania and South Sudan.

SHT25 sensor		✓			25
Soil Moisture sensor			✓		25
Soil temperature sensor			✓		25
Solar Insolation sensor	✓				25
Super capacitors	✓	✓	✓		75
Terminal blocks	✓	✓	✓	✓	
TP 4056 Battery protector				✓	25
Wind Speed sensor	✓				15

1.1 Procurement process

Given the requirements in Table 1, procurement was initiated at Makerere University, which is one of the project implementers. The procurement process was supposed to follow the government of Uganda procurement guidelines[3]. First step was to look for suppliers for each of the equipment, get quotations from each supplier and select one supplier for each component. Uganda Revenue Authority exempted the project from paying taxes on the project equipment imported.

Table 2. List of suppliers and their contacts

No.	Item	Quantity	Supplier	Contact Details
	Enclosures			
1	White enclosure Box	75	Marlanvil	Nadia
2	Large White enclosure Box	25	Innovex	Innovex
3	Interior decorations: for nodes; sensor holders, PVC sensor tube; i2c-cable holder; photodiode holder and metal film resistors	25	SA0BXI Systems	Prof. Bjorn Pehrson
4	glands	125	ZHEJIANG ARTS & CRAFTS IMPORT & EXPORT CO., LTD	Maggie Wu <eiaa@leinoer.com
5	Pagoda	25		Fischer
6	Metallic frame (fabrication+nuts & bolts)	25	CEDAT Metal Workshop	Mr. Kasakye. CEDAT Fabrication Workshop
7	Concrete / Civil Works	25		
8	Consumables	many	Innovex	Innovex
	Electronics			
9	RS S2-Motes	70	Radio Sensors	Radio Sensors
10	I2c Daughter Card ADC	25	Radio Sensors	Radio Sensors
11	I2c Daughter Card TRH	25	Radio Sensors	Radio Sensors
12	I2c Daughter Card AtmP	25	Radio Sensors	Radio Sensors
13	Photo diodes	25	Farnell	
14	Lithium Ion Capacitors	75	Sealtron	Faizal / Cheryl
15	PSU	75		
16	Raspberry Pis	10	No specific supplier	
17	DS3231 RTCs clock modules	25		
18	Modems	25	Electron / Aliexpress	
19	SD card modules	25	No specific supplier	

	External sensors			
20	Diffusors (White teflon sheets (150*150mm, thickness 3mm))	3		Bill
21	Inspeed wind gauges + shipping	25	Inspeed	
22	VH400 soil moisture + shipping	25		
23	DS18B20 soil temperature + shipping ?	25	Guangzhou JianYuan Electronics Co. Ltd	Amanda Rao: amanda@jysensor.cn
24	7852 Davis Rain gauge + shipping to Uganda	25	Scientific Sales Inc.	Thomas S. Tesauro, Sr. Scientific Sales, Inc. P.O. Box 6725 Lawrenceville, NJ 08648. Tel: 609.844.0055 Fax: 609.844.0466 email:"Scientific Sales, Inc." <sales@scientificsales.com> / tom@scientificsales.com
25	AWS Labelling	25		
26	PCB	25		

The AWS stands shall be fabricated from each of the three countries since they are heavy and materials are locally available. Table 3 gives details of raw materials for fabricating the stands

Figure 1. The 9 stands that were fabricated at Makerere University

Table 3. Costs for fabricating AWS stands in Kampala, Uganda [1 USD was estimated at UGX 3,700]

Item	Specifications	Unit Cost	Qty	Total Cost (UGX)
Pipes mild Steel	76mm diameter x2 mm thickness x 6 m length	65,085.00	9	585,765.00
Pipes mild Steel	63mm diameter x2 mm thickness x 6 m length	59800	9	538,200.00
Pipes mild Steel	32mm diameter x1.5 mm thickness x 6 m length	22,350.00	3	67,050.00
Pipes mild Steel	25x25x3	41,550.00	7	290,850.00
welding rhodes	3.2m	25,000.00	4	100,000.00
paint (silver/aluminium)	1ltr	23,000.00	9	207,000.00
thinner (best quality)	1ltr	15,000.00	4	60,000.00
Labor		150,000.00	9	1,350,000.00
Transport				250,000.00
Metal plates	6mm thick, 4 inchx8 inch	343,178.00	2	686,356.00
Total				4,135,221.00

1.2 Pre-deployment preparations and site selection and Visits

Proposals of areas to deploy the AWSs were received from the three countries and in collaboration with the meteorological services, including Tanzania Meteorological Authority(TMA) [4], Uganda National Meteorological Authority (UNMA) [5] and South Sudan Meteorological Services. Below are the proposed sites:-

Table 4. Proposed sites in Uganda

Name	Stn_Id	Longitude	Latitude	Altitude	District
Abi Estate	86300020	03 05 N	030 57 E	1,170.0	Arua
Arua Met Station	863000101	30.917	3.05	1280	Arua
Entebbe NMC	89320660	31.36666667	0.5833333333		Entebbe
Entebbe WDD	89320750	32.467	0.05	1128	Entebbe
Jinja Met. Station	89330430	33.183	0.45	1175	Jinja
Kabale Met Station		29.983	-1.25	1869	KABALE
Kasese Met Station	89300630	30.1	0.183	691	Kasese

Makerere University		32.633	0.25	1200	Kampala
Masindi Met Station		31.717	1.683	1147	Masindi
Mbarara Met Station	90300030	30.683	-0.6	1420	Mbarara
Soroti Met Station		33.617	1.717	1132	Serere
Tororo Met.Station		34.167	0.683	1170	Tororo

In Uganda, we prepared a site visit plan to establish the requirements for the sites and to choose the most suitable among the options provided by UNMA. Below is a guide for testing the suitability of a given site for deployment.

Table 5. Checklist to follow during the site visits and in selecting suitable sites for deployment

No.	Requirement	Reason/ Comment
1	Signal strength	This is important because the stations might use GSM/GPRS for Internet connection. Which telecom company's signal is the best? How to do this?
2	Possibility of other uplink methods (eg Ethernet)	May be preferred because it could be more reliable than using modems and in the long run become cheaper
3	Security	Very likely especially since we are installing in places with existing stations. However, new sites will require checks on security
4	MET Personnel/Observers skills	What skills do the available staff in charge of the sites have? Any people willing to participate in the deployment especially in hiring people for concrete works? What about their work schedule? Do they already know about WIMEA-ICT and willing to assist?
5	Distance from meteorological office	If near, the station will have more chances of getting access to services such as power and Internet
6	Status of stations with which to benchmark	We need to ensure we benchmark with a reliable station for a fair comparison.
7	What parameters existing station collects	We need to ensure there are a good number of parameters common to the WIMEA-ICT site
8	How far the site is form the assembly point	For better transport planning
9	Climatic Zone	We want to ensure that we install in all the climatic zones
10	Grid power	If possible, to know if the station might have access to power
11	Contact person	During the maintenance stage, we might require minor troubleshooting without necessarily accessing the station. Also, the person should be available during the training and deployment

12	Space availability	
13	Any support tools available	For example, ladder, computer, tool box, water, water containers especially for the concrete works, etc which can be used during maintenance and deployment to help WIMEA-ICT make the necessary arrangements
14	Any caged stands for putting things like batteries?	
15	Availability of casual laborers	If available, they must be notified earlier

2. Assembly

2.1. Item Grouping

Four big boxes were prepared and labelled (sink, grd, 10m and 2m) to hold the 4 nodes. 25 marlavin boxes as in Figure 3 were placed in each of the boxes. After grouping the equipment, some nodes were incomplete because of the following reasons

- i. Some equipment had not yet arrived e.g. Soil temperature sensors, PCB for the low power gateway
- ii. Some equipment previously planned for Gen 3 were used in field tests
- iii. Some suppliers had not yet responded
- iv. Some items had never been planned for e.g. Glue

Because of the above reasons, assembly was postponed until all the expected items had been delivered, which was approximated to late July 2018.

Figure 2. Boxes containing marlavin boxes in which to place the sink nodes. Other nodes were also placed in a similar box

Figure 3. Contents of the sink node

2.2 Configuring the Nodes

Each of the nodes was configured to transmit every 60 seconds and the report mask, representing which parameters to transmit, modified accordingly. Details of the configuration of the RSS2 nodes and raspberry pi are given in the Appendix and manuals

2.2 Preparing the Low-power gateway

Procedure for setting up the Gen-3 low power gateway sink node:

Software required:

1. Particle desktop development environment: particle IDE [6]
2. Particle CLI (command line interface): command line interface [7]
3. winAvr:

Since the gateway uses both the RSS2 node and particle electron modules, software for both RSS2 node and electron is required. Setting up this software is fully detailed in the above provided links

Below is the detailed procedure used:

- Create a file on the SD-card called config.txt. This file contains configuration details, like the APN used, number of reports to be received from the mote before uploading to the

server, the name of the server to upload to, the port on the server to connect to, username, and password. This file makes it easy to change these connection parameters without reprogramming the particle electron, since the electron reads the file and uses these parameters in its firmware.

- The RSS2-mote used for the gateway is programmed with gen3sink.hex or gen3sink.avr-rss2 firmware[8]. The mote receives reports from any other broadcasting motes, indicated by the red LED on the board blinking, it appends a time stamp to it from the RTC module and sends it through its serial interface to the electron. After every 30 seconds the mote also sends its own report to the serial port, indicated by a blinking yellow LED.
- The particle electron is programmed with the binary file produced after compiling gen3-gw.ino file[9]. This firmware enables the electron to alternate between sleep and awake state. Initially, the electron is asleep, it's woken by an interrupt on D1 when the mote sends a report. It receives the report on its serial port, creates a file on the SD-card, and writes the report to it

Hardware setup:

Requirements:

1. particle electron 3g module
2. WIMEA-ICT PCB
3. 1 RSS2-sink mote
4. 1 SD card module and an SD card
5. 1 ds3231 RTC module
6. Mini SIM of any preference
7. 3.7v li-ion battery pack
8. 1 Li-ion battery charging protection circuit
9. 2.5W solar panel

Tools used:

1. Solder iron and solder metal
2. Female SIP headers, female angled SIP headers
3. Male SIP headers

The WIMEA-ICT PCB is designed to easily interface the low power gateway components for robustness, power sharing and for easy deployment. The design connects the RSS2-sink node to the ds3131 RTC module over i2c interface using the female angled SIP headers, the SD-card module is connected to the particle electron over SPI. The board also provides power connection for the electron and the sink node as show in the Figure 5.

Figure 4: WIMEA-ICT PCB schematic

Procedure for setting up the Low power gateway:

1. Solder female SIP headers onto board in the position of the particle electron 3G, making sure they are leveled and the board balances well on them
2. Solder into place, female SIP headers to hold the SD-card and RTC modules
3. Solder angled female SIP headers into place for the mote_i2c interface
4. Solder male SIP headers into the positions marked j1, B1, B0, TX, Rx, D1, D0 and DIP male headers to the power port marked PWR.
5. Jumpers J4 and J5 do not need to be soldered unless using a Li-ion battery packaged with its own protection circuit when purchased. For easy hardware debugging preferences, we used an external charging protection circuit (TP4D56), hence did not need jumpers J5 and J4. The TP4D56 fits directly into the male SIP headers
6. Solder an XHT female header to hold the battery in the position marked BAT.
7. Solder a DIP switch in the position marked switch on the board

Jumper J1 connects the V-Bat pin on particle electron to the battery power, this pin can be removed depending on how you want to power the electron. When programming the particle electron it's preferred that this jumper is removed.

Pins D1 on the board is connected to RSS2-mote's port marked CON-INT5, in the middle position. This serves as an interrupt source to the electron, to wake it up whenever it sends a report. Pins B1, B0 and D0 are used for general debugging of the particle electron.

Pins marked RXD, and TXT on the board are connected to the serial port of the RSS2-mote so as to send reports to the electron.

A male XHT power connector can be used to power the RSS2-mote from any one pair of pins soldered on the power port of the board.

Your setup should have a fair resemblance to this after doing the above steps

Figure 5: The gen-3 sink Low Power gateway

After making the necessary connections, connecting a battery, and turning on switch, you should see the sink mote power up with a couple of blinks on the yellow led, and the particle electron RGB blinking white.

We observed that its better to manually reset the sink mote after powering up, by pressing its reset button. After reset, you should observe the RGB of the electron alternate between on and off meaning between awake and sleep state. The frequency of the alternation depends on the frequency of any other broadcasting motes in close proximity to the sink node. Depending on your config.txt settings, specifically UPLOADCOUNT, the electron should then attempt to connect to a cellular network ie blinking green, and breathing green when connected to your specified server and port. After uploading, the electron disconnects from the network and goes back to the alternating wake and sleep function.

Debugging pointers:

1. 5 fast RED blinks on the electron RGB: the SD-card initialization has failed. Double check the integrity of your SD-card
2. RGB blinking green and failing to establish a server connection.
Check your configuration file on the SD card. Make sure each setting is on a new line like below
APN:internet
USERNAME:

PASS:
UPLOADCOUNT:30
SERVER:wimea.mak.ac.ug
PORT:10100
DUMMY: data

Figure 6. PCB for the WIMEA-ICT Low power gateway

Figure 7. Workstation during assembly of the Low power gateway

Table 6. BCB for the Low Power Gateway with particle electron and battery attached.

Figure 8. Setting time and date on the RTC, using firmware

3. Readiness Assessment

This section assesses the readiness to deploy Gen 3 WIMEA-ICT AWSs including processes that have been explored to ensure their smooth deployment.

- Partner institutions have been working hand in hand with the Meteorological services of Uganda, Tanzania and South Sudan to ensure that through their mandate, the process of testing and deployment of the AWS AWS is successful. This has been done through signing memorandum of understandings which stipulate commitment of the two parties.
- **Equipment:** The equipment for the 25 AWSs were procured on behalf of the three partner institutions and delivered to Makerere University, Uganda. However, since some equipment has been used during the testing phase, ONLY 21 AWSs shall be deployed in the first phase. 2 stations shall go to South Sudan, 11 to Tanzania and 8 to be installed in Uganda. Makerere University has already fabricated 9 AWS stands However, the two other partners are yet to start fabricating some.
- **Taxes:** The three partner institutions of the project have already acquired tax exemption from the revenue bodies. As such, all equipment that is imported under WIMEA-ICT project is exempted from the taxes.
- **Capacity building:** For the past 20 months, the project through its lab has trained over 30 students from both Computing and Electrical Engineering backgrounds. These two groups have always supplemented each other in setting up the AWSs. Also, the main stakeholder, the metrological services (Uganda and South Sudan) have been trained on how to set up the AWS. Table 7 gives details of aspects that were emphasized during the training. Metrological representatives included those from the stations network department, forecasters and from the meteorological school. It was however observed that the time was limited for meteorological services representatives to have a grasp of the concepts. Also, members did not have the required background to understand the concepts that were prepared and as such considered all aspects of the training new.

Table 7. Training program used at UoJ and Mekerere

	Activity	Level	Duration/hrs
1	Overview of AWS and communication architecture (Components, purpose, part numbers) Sensor Nodes hardware features, Interfaces and support hardware (FTDI cables, jumper wires)	Basic	1
2	Basic Operations (Connecting solar panel, changing SD Card), Power supply troubleshooting (ATMEGA256RFR2 Gateway, RASPBERRY Pi , sensor nodes)	Basic	0.5

3	Linux Basics	Basic	1
4	Sensor node configuration and serial terminals (report masks, interval, booting details), Accessing, upgrading firmware (bootloader and application)	Medium	1
5	Raspberry pi Gateway (Installing Rasbian, setting up and troubleshooting sensd)	Basic	1
6	Advanced Linux (setting up cron jobs, web server, RTC basics)	Medium	0.5
7	ATMEGA256RFR2 Gateway(operations and Basic Troubleshooting)	Medium	1
8	Uplinks (web tunnelling, modem , WiFi)	Technical	1
9	AWS Installation and Assembly	Basic	0.5
10	Capturing, analyzing and Interpreting AWS Data (Tools and methods)	Medium	2
11	Remote Monitoring (SSH, HTTP), Basic Troubleshooting (sink node, uplink), Identifying imminent issues	Basic	1.5

- **Testing:** Testing and improvement of the AWS has been ongoing for 2 years and currently, the station is able to last a long time because of the improvements.
- **Selecting sites for deployment:** A number of locations were obtained by the three partner institutions from the meteorological services. The tables 8 and 9 show the list of proposed sites for deployment. Appendix 4 has the findings of two of the proposed sites in Uganda

Table 8. Proposed sites for South Sudan

SITE	Location	Proposed Radius(<)
NIMULE	LONG32.05,LAT 3.61	200m
WAU – SITE1	LONG27.97,LAT 7.70	200m
SITE2	LONG27.96,LAT 7.71	200m
RAJA	LONG25.67,LAT 8.47	200m
MALAKAL	LONG31.67,LAT 9.57	200m
PALOICH	LONG32.54,LAT 10.45	200m
BOR – SITE1	LONG31.57,LAT 6.21	200m
SITE2	LONG31.6,LAT 6.19	200m
SITE3	LONG31.55,LAT 6.21	200m
TAMBURA	LONG27.47,LAT 5.60	200m

PIBOR	LONG33.13,LAT 6.79	200m
AYOD	LONG31.40,LAT 8.11	200m
KAPOETA	LONG33.59,LAT 4.77	200m

Table 9. Proposed sites for Uganda

Name	Stn_Id	Longitude	Latitude	Altitude	District
Abi Estate	86300020	03 05 N	030 57 E	1,170.0	Arua
Arua Met Station	863000101	30.917	3.05	1280	Arua
Entebbe NMC	89320660	31.36666667	0.5833333333		Entebbe
Entebbe WDD	89320750	32.467	0.05	1128	Entebbe
Jinja Met. Station	89330430	33.183	0.45	1175	Jinja
Kabale Met Station		29.983	-1.25	1869	KABALE
Kasese Met Station	89300630	30.1	0.183	691	Kasese
Makerere University		32.633	0.25	1200	Kampala
Masindi Met Station		31.717	1.683	1147	Masindi
Mbarara Met Station	90300030	30.683	-0.6	1420	Mbarara
Soroti Met Station		33.617	1.717	1132	Serere
Tororo Met.Station		34.167	0.683	1170	Tororo

- Assessing resources for deploying AWSs. Below is the tentative sketch of requirements for assessing the suitability of the deployment sites. Where more sites were provided than available AWSs, sites that satisfy the biggest number of requirements should be selected. Table 10 shows the checklist used to assess the suitability of the sites in Uganda. UNMA proposed installing the AWSs alongside the existing stations for the first few months for benchmarking purposes.

Table 10. Checklist for selecting where to install the first batch of WIMEA-ICT AWSs and assessing the needs for installing them

No.	Requirement	Comments
1	Signal strength	This is important because the stations might use GSM/GPRS for Internet connection. Which telecom company's signal is the best? How to do this?
2	Possibility of other uplink methods (e.g. Ethernet)	May be preferred because it could be more reliable than using modems and in the long run become cheaper
3	Security	Very likely to be secure especially since we are installing in places with existing stations. However, new sites will require checks on security

4	MET Personnel/Observers skills	What skills do the available staff in charge of the sites have? Any people willing to participate in the deployment especially in hiring people for concrete works? What about their work schedule? Do they already know about WIMEA-ICT and willing to assist?
5	Distance from meteorological office	If near, the station will have more chances of getting access to services such as power and Internet
6	Status of stations with which to benchmark	We need to ensure we benchmark with a reliable station for a fair comparison.
7	What parameters existing station collects	We need to ensure there are a good number of parameters common to the WIMEA-ICT site
8	How far the site is from the assembly point	For better transport planning
9	Climatic Zone	We want to ensure that we install in all the climatic zones
10	Grid power	If possible, to know if the station might have access to power
11	Contact person	During the maintenance stage, we might require minor troubleshooting without necessarily accessing the station. Also, the person should be available during the training and deployment
12	Space availability	
13	Any support tools available	For example, ladder, computer, tool box, water, jerrycans especially for the concrete works, etc which can be used during maintenance and deployment to help WIMEA-ICT make the necessary arrangements
14	Any caged stands for putting things like batteries?	
15	Availability of casual laborers	If available, they must be notified earlier

Additional recommendations from South Sudan Meteorological service are as below

- Deploy the equipment at an optimum distance from the base station as per the coordinates.
- Due to inherent nature of 3G coverage, which causes “cell breathing” whereby the coverage shrinks and expands depending on the system load, in case of high usage of resources the coverage will shrink and when the users decrease the coverage returns to normal. The equipment should be deployed at a proposed distance of 200m maximum from the base station to minimize effects of network coverage issues.
- The highest extended quality of service parameters should be applied for the SIMs to be used in the Zain dongles for the weather stations. It’s recommended to apply a maximum uplink bit rate of 7 mbit/s and also to attain guaranteed uplink bit rate of 384 kbit/s so as to ensure data can be uploaded from the weather stations to the remote servers without facing any bandwidth bottlenecks.

4. Dispatch plans

After assembling the AWS components in Makerere University, some were to be transported to Dar-es-salaam Institute of Technology and others to University of Juba (UoJ), South Sudan. Since there are a number of students from UoJ currently studying from Makerere University, we plan to explore the options of the students taking along the equipment on their way for their holidays. Two AWSs have already been transported to UoJ by bus by a student, a process that ensured safety of the equipment. Below are the considerations we made during the preparation for dispatch of the equipment

- Components should be placed in the white marlavin boxes to prevent damages that may result from transportation. The equipment shall also be protected from damage by placing shock absorbers between the boxes.
- Each consignment shall be accompanied by an introductory letter, which states the purpose of the equipment and the content
- The power shall be disconnected during transportation and re-connected during the deployment

5. Possible Unforeseen Challenges

Below are some of the challenges that may be faced, hence the need to make the necessary arrangements:

- Administrative challenges: The project needs to enforce constant communication with the meteorological services.
- Limited resources at the sites of deployment could limit the amount of data delivered to the repository and limit maintenance abilities.
- Lack of a server for sending UoJ data. Gen 2 WIMEA-ICT AWS prototype at UoJ was configured to send data to Makerere University, which is unsustainable.
- Lack of public IP addresses for the stations, which will be using the raspberry pi as their gateway. Currently the few available stations are using the wimea-ic.net domain to tunnel traffic to the Internet. This has been a challenge for the station, which was installed at UoJ most likely because of the poor Internet signals.
- The training provided was insufficient and members require much more training in order to start using the stations. This will lead to limited maintenance level for the stations
- The sites selected as possible locations for deployment especially in South Sudan may not be protected from Vandals and yet this was never planned by the project.
- The AWS stands are big and require big vehicles to transport. Transporting a single station to a far-off site requires huge transportation costs.
- We assume that each site of deployment has the necessary tools to support the deployment and maintenance of the AWSs. Such equipment includes ladders, water for the concrete works for setting up the stands, Ethernet ports for AWSs using the raspberry for their gateway, screw drivers, extra nodes for testing the deployments, etc It may not be true that all these shall be available and as such challenge the deployment process
- Due to many factors such as harsh weather and others, some equipment might get spoilt. Currently, there are no available spares, which may increase down time when such equipment fail.
- Lack of space especially for UoJ to store equipment and from where to assemble. This space is necessary since the equipment are fragile and may be stolen if not secured.

6. Recommendations

- Since University of Juba does not have a member on the project to spearhead the deployment of the AWSs, the current masters students may be trained in order to support the process. As such, the students shall be trained in order to understand the operations of the AWS.
- Since South Sudan has no power and Internet is a challenge in many areas, all the AWSs that shall be sent for deployment shall only use the low power gateway, which uses very low power.
- The team should ensure that all partners have secured adequate space for storing the equipment before they are transported. Also, since there is an inventory management system, other partners can be allowed to use it to track the equipment.
- The project should prepare more comprehensive a longer training sessions for the meteorological services staff. Makerere has already invited UNMA members to join the WIMEA-ICT lab for a period of over two weeks in order to train them on a wider variety of WIMEA-ICT AWS sections.
- UoJ should start exploring options of using servers at the meteorological service.
- The project could choose a meteorological school as one of the sites for deploying the AWSs such that training of the new technologies becomes continuous.

7. Documentation and other resources

In order to provide the support needed to setup, assemble and deploy the WIMEA-ICT AWS, several manuals can be found including

- RSS2 node user manual from <https://zenodo.org/record/1343888#.W27f7NIzaM8>
- RSS2 noted technical manual <https://zenodo.org/record/1343890#.W27hYNIzaM8>
- Setting up the Low Power gateway
- Setting up WIMEA-ICT AWS <https://zenodo.org/record/1343892#.W27iP9IzaM8>
- Downloading RSS2 node Proprietary application firmware from <http://radio-sensors.com/download/firmware/S2/AtMega256RFR2/>
- Downloading RSS2 node bootloader from <http://radio-sensors.com/download/firmware/S2/AtMega256RFR2/>
- Downloading open-source RSS2 application firmware from <https://github.com/wimea-ict/contiki/tree/master/platform/avr-rss2/apps/wimea-ict-rss2> (.hex file)
- Downloading contiki for RSS2 node <https://github.com/wimea-ict/contiki/>

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- [15] “Passwordless SSH access.”

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Appendix 1: The team

No.	Names	Technical Background
1	Dr. Julianne Sansa Otim	Computing
2	Maximum Byamukama	Electrical Engineering
3	Mary Nsabagwa	Computing
4	Mukwaya Nicholas	Computing
5	Doreen Nerima	Computing
6	Kabali Michael	Computing
7	Mwesigwa Robert	Computing
8	Mbabazi Angella	Computing
9	Omilya Isaac	Computing
10	Nisiima Grace	Computing
11	Joshua Muhumuza	Computing
12	Robert Kasumba	Computing
13	Joel Okello	Computing
14	Tukesiga Ian	Computing
15	Alinitwe Sandra Kamugisha	Computing
16	Munyira Samson	Computing
17	Kasozi Mulondo Moses	Computing
18	Mutesasira Jovan	Computing
19	Kyebambe Sarah	Computing
20	Tumwesigye Eugene Owak	Computing
21	Dihfahsih Mugoya	Computing
22	Suuna Conrad	Computing
23	Ainekirabo Mbabazi	Computing
24	Freedom Gemmar	Computing
25	Kamira Moses	Computing
26	Trevor Nagaba	Electrical Engineering
27	Abaho Alvin	Electrical Engineering
28	Quinton Ssebagala	Electrical Engineering
29	Kabonire Ruhinda	Electrical Engineering
30	DeoOkedi	Electrical Engineering
31	Ruth Agaba	Electrical Engineering

Appendix 2: Frequent Problems and Possible Solutions

Common problems, as faced during the testing period are given in the table under the categories including

- Configurations
- Power supply
- Gateway

No.	Problem/Sign	Solution	Category
1	Resetting of the date at the raspberry pi to 1970	Constant power supply or a script that picks a date from google and resets the date. The script can run on the next time the raspberry pi starts or as a cron job	Gateway
2	Failure of nodes to transmit some parameters	Check if the sensor is faulty, check loose connections. Check if parameter was configured	Node and sensor
3	Failure to receive from a node after a long time	Check power supply of the node. If working remotely, check the voltage that was sent in the previous reports	
4	Failure to receive information from the AWS	Power or Internet problems. The raspberry pi's SD card may have slipped out.	
5	Poor signal causing packet dropping	Check RSSI and Link Quality Values	
6	Failure of the node to store reports on the raspberry pi	Check to see if sensd is running Check to confirm if the configurations of the COM port are correct Confirm if data is being received Confirm if the node is attached and is transmitting Check the report interval Check to see if the file that saves the weather information has write permissions	
7	Wind speed values above 0 but wind direction reading 0	Check status of the sensors	

Appendix 3: Steps in setting up and configuring WIMEA-ICT AWS

8.1. Introduction

This is a technical manual for WIMEA-ICT Automatic Weather Station (AWS). The AWS is based on Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN). The AWS prototype consists of 4 wireless sensor nodes and a Raspberry Pi acting as a gateway. The sink node has a wired connection to the raspberry Pi. The sensors are connected to the nodes as follows:

- i. The 10m node has wind direction and speed and solar insolation sensors. The node is installed 10m from the ground.
- ii. The 2m node has air temperature and humidity sensor (SHT25 sensor). The SHT25 sensor is installed 2m from the ground along the AWS 10m stand.
- iii. The ground node has the soil temperature, soil moisture sensor and rain gauge. The soil sensors are in the soil while the rain gauge is either on the ground or close to the ground.
- iv. The sink node has an atmospheric pressure sensor and is attached to and powered by the Raspberry Pi forming a gateway. The gateway is powered through its USB port using a 5V AC-DC adapter.

8.2. Wireless sensor Node

8.2.1 Features of RSS2 Mote

WIMEA-ICT AWS uses a radio sensor node/mote, also called RSS2 mote from radio sensors [10]. Figures 1 and 2 show the back and front views of the node

Figure 9 Front side of RSS2 Mote

Sensors may be attached to interfaces including INT5, ADC1 etc. The reset button is used to reset the mote. This is normally done during writing the bootloader. When configuring the mote, an FTDI cable in may be connected to the mote through a USB-TTL 6-pin connector. Figure 3 and 4 show ftdi cable.

Figure 10 Back side of RSS2 Mote

The mote uses IEEE 802.15.4 wireless protocol to communicate i.e. receive and send packets. When installing the AWS, the antenna coverage label must face the sink node for a good signal.

Figure 11 FTDI cable showing the two ends

Figure 12 Head of FTDI Cable, which connects to the Mote

8.2.2 Configuring the RSS2 Mote

In order to configure the mote, connect the mote to a computer running an ssh client like putty using an ftdi cable. In case of Linux, other serial communication clients like minicom may be used. First check the serial port used by the mote under device manager as in Figure 5 .

Figure 13 Device manager showing COM17 Port in windows after connecting the mote via ftdi cable

After identifying the COM port, use a client of your choice. For example, putty as per Figure 6. Under Connection Type, select Serial. Ensure that the speed is 38400. Select Open and interact with the serial Interface.

Figure 14 Putty, a serial client opting to use com port 17.

After pressing the Open button, you will be able to interact with the mote via keyboard commands. Figure 7 shows a sample of commands provided during the mote configuration. Follow the commands to perform configuration.

```

h-help
ri- How often the reporting is done, in seconds eg ri 60 – report every 1 minute
re –display report mask ,
eg re #0 txt,e64,t (sets the report number 0 to report node name, mac address
and temperature )
ss- Display system summary

```

Figure 15 Connecting the Mote to Raspberry Pi GPIO pins using jumper wires

8.3. Gateway Configuration

The gateway is a combination of a node, also known as a sink because of its function and Raspberry pi. The gateway enables the AWS to connect to the Internet. Connecting the AWS to Internet enables users to remotely access it. The sink collects data from all other nodes and stores it on the raspberry pi. Using any uplink option/ Internet connection method, the data may be accessed from anywhere at any time.

8.3.1 Installing and setting up the raspberry Pi

The raspberry Pi is equipped with many interfaces including USB ports (4), HDMI port, power slot and SD card slot among others. It however does not have a monitor. The HDMI interface provides a connection of the raspberry pi to a computer using HDMI to VGA cable. A keyboard and mouse may also be connected to the raspberry pi via the USB interfaces.

There are various operating systems, which may be installed on the raspberry pi. The operating systems should reside on an SD card, which is placed in the SD card slot. First, the operating system must be set up on the SD card, An example of an OS is Rasbian Wheezy.

Install Win32DiskImager on your computer. The software will help to write the operating system to the SD card. Follow instructions on [11].

After writing the OS, insert the SD card into the raspberry pi and power it. More instructions on setting up the raspberry pi may be found at [12].

8.3.2 Connecting Node to Raspberry Pi

The following Figures show how the RSS2 mote is connected to the raspberry pi using female jumper wires.

Figure 16 Part of the RSS2 Mote showing how which pins are connected to the raspberry Pi

Figure 17 Part of the Raspberry Pi showing the GPIO pins to which the node pins are connected using jumper wires

An alternative option of connecting the node to the raspberry pi is by using an ftdi cable. I.e. connect the USB of the cable to the USB port of the raspberry pi

8.3.3 Connecting Gateway to Internet

There are various ways of connecting the raspberry pi to Internet. These include

1. Using cable via ther Ethernet interface
2. Wifi, by attaching a wifi dongle to the raspberry pi
3. Using a USB modem
4. Etc

Options 1 requires no configuration, while option 2 requires limited configurations. Option 3 requires massive configurations and details are given in this document.

8.3.3.1 Configuring Raspberry Pi to Connect to Internet Using a USB Modem

Below is a list of required software for the raspberry Pi

Table 11 Required Raspberry Pi software

Software	Function
ppp	Manages connection between the Raspberry Pi and 3g Provider
Sakis3g	Connects to 3G Internet via a configured Sim card
UMTSkeeper	To reconnect the 3G dongle using sakis3g script if connection drops

Although the Raspberry pi has an Ethernet port for Internet connection, in the absence of cable, alternatives including using wifi and USB modems may be used

To configure the raspberry pi to access Internet using usb modem, perform the following tasks:-

- i. Edit `/etc/network/interfaces` to have the following
Auto usb0
Allow-hotplug usb0
Iface usb0 inet dhcp
- ii. In case of a smart mobile phone, set USB tethering and check connection by pinging any site.(Optional step but may help to access Internet before configuring the modem)
- iii. Follow instructions on [13] to set up sakis 3g on the raspberry pi
- iv. Install ppp
- v. Install umtskeeper `sudo wget http://zool33.uni-graz.at/petz/umtkeeper/src/umtskeeper.tar.gz`

8.4. Data

8.4.1 Acquiring data from AWS

Given an active Internet connection, the AWS data may be accessed via SSH or a web page, which runs on the gateway, a raspberry Pi. For a gateway with a public IP address, SSH access may be performed through direct SSH using IP address or domain name, username and password of the raspberry Pi. Different SSH clients may be used including putty, which has versions for both windows and Linux. Linux users may issue the SSH commands via the terminal.

A gateway using a dynamic or private address may not be directly accessed remotely. It can however be accessed through reverse tunneling, which enables the gateway traffic to go through a public IP server. While at the public IP server, the pi may be accessed. follow instructions on [14] to configure reverse tunneling on the gateway. Also, ensure that the raspberry pi's SSH public key is added to the public servers authorized keys to enable raspberry pi to login into server without asking for a password. Refer to [15] to configure password-less SSH access from raspberry pi to server.

Figure 18 Using putty, an ssh client to access the public IP server

8.4.2 Data Analysis

Data is recorded in a text file, containing key/value pairs, organized in rows. Each row represents a transmission of a mixture of weather parameters, voltage and network information and starts with a date and time in the first two columns. Figure 2 shows a sample text file for a WIMEA-ICT AWS

```
2016-12-06 09:28:08 TZ=UTC UT=1481016488 GW_LAT=32.57100 GW_LON=0.32920 &:
TXT=makg2-2m E64=fcc23d00000182b5 PS=1 V_MCU=2.92 V_IN=3.68 T_SHT2X=29.61
RH_SHT2X=36.15 [ADDR=31.193 SEQ=103 TTL=15 RSSI=24 LQI=255 DRP=0.00]
2016-12-06 09:28:08 TZ=UTC UT=1481016488 GW_LAT=32.57100 GW_LON=0.32920 &:
TXT=makg2-2m E64=fcc23d00000182b5 PS=1 V_MCU=2.92 V_IN=3.68 T_SHT2X=29.61
RH_SHT2X=36.15 [ADDR=31.193 SEQ=103 TTL=14 RSSI=1 LQI=255 DRP=0.00]
2016-12-06 09:28:08 TZ=UTC UT=1481016488 GW_LAT=32.57100 GW_LON=0.32920 &:
TXT=makg2-gnd PS=1 P0=0x0 P0_LST60=0 UP=0x16108 V_A1=0.04 V_A2=2.95
[ADDR=133.199 SEQ=204 TTL=15 RSSI=26 LQI=255 DRP=0.00]
2016-12-06 09:28:08 TZ=UTC UT=1481016488 GW_LAT=32.57100 GW_LON=0.32920 &:
TXT=makg2-gnd PS=1 P0=0x0 P0_LST60=0 UP=0x16108 V_A1=0.04 V_A2=2.95
[ADDR=133.199 SEQ=204 TTL=14 RSSI=2 LQI=255 DRP=0.00]
2016-12-06 09:28:08 TZ=UTC UT=1481016488 GW_LAT=32.57100 GW_LON=0.32920 &:
TXT=makg2-gnd PS=1 T=33.25 T1=27.06 V_MCU=3.00 V_IN=3.85 [ADDR=133.199
SEQ=205 TTL=15 RSSI=26 LQI=255 DRP=0.00]
```

Figure 19 Sample WIMEA-ICT AWS text file

Besides date and time, there are other columns such as those in Table 1

Table 12 WIMEA-ICT AWS Database file key representations

Node	Abbreviation	Parameter
To All Nodes	TZ	Timezone
	GW_LAT	Gateway Latitude
	GW_LON	Gateway Longitude
	TXT	Text assigned to node for identification purposes
	E64	Mac Address of Node
10m		
	V_MCU	Microcontroller Voltage
	P0_T	
	V_A1	Wind Speed
	V_A2	Wind direction
	T	Temperature sensor reading
2m	T_SHT2X	Temperature reading from SHT 25
	RH_SHT2X	Humidity reading from SHT25
	V_MCU	Microcontroller Voltage

GND	PS	Power save indicator
	T	Air temperature reading
	T1	Soil temperature
	V_MCU	MCU input voltage
	V_IN	Input voltage
	V_A1	Soil moisture
Sink		

8.4.3 Data Extraction

Before data analysis, extracting and formatting it is necessary especially for benchmarking or research purposes. In order to format, organize or filter out required data, `seltag` a software, which is compiled with `sensd` [16] is used. `Sensd` can be downloaded from

For example, in order to format 2m data to display columns containing date, temperature and relative humidity, issue the following `seltag` command, extracted from `data_file` and writing sorted data to `2m.dat`

```
more data_file.dat | grep 2m | grep ^20 | seltag -sel T_SHT2X=%s RH_SHT2X=%s | grep -v Miss >> 2m.dat
```

The formatted data may help in plotting data

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Appendix 4:REPORT ON SITE VISIT FINDINGS BY KASUMBA ROBERT and KABONIRE RUHINDA CARRIED OUT AT MUBENDE MET STATION AND MBARARA MET STATION ON 09th January, 2018 AND 10th January, 2018.

MUBENDE SITE

Requirement	Field Finding
Signal strength	MTN signal strength was better , Airtel was fairly strong. Screen shots of the Network Cell Info app are provided in the folders MUBENDE_SITE_RUHINDA and UBENDE_SITE_KASUMBA.
Possibility of other uplink methods (eg Ethernet)	There is no possibility of other uplink methods except use of modem.
Security	The station has a fence as the only security mechanism.
MET Personnel/Observers skills	The two personnel indicated that they have sufficient computer knowledge. They promised that they would help in mobilising labor in case they are briefed before the deployment is carried out at the station. Their work schedules are flexible since they only have to

	read parameters only twice a day. They didn't have any prior knowledge about WIMEA-ICT.
Distance from meteorological office	The Mubende Weather station is a hydromet station (parameters are read only twice a day) and thus they don't have a MET office. According to Mr. Milton Waiswa, the MET offices are only found at synoptic weather stations. The closest power source to the station would be from the house of the Monitors which is about 10m from the station.
Status of stations with which to benchmark	Mr. Dhikusooka indicated that they get problems with the current weather stations though they are not so often. He however indicated that the manual one is very reliable.
What parameters existing station collects	Rainfall, wind speed, Dry Bulb, Wet bulb, wind direction, Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature, sunshine
How far the site is from the assembly point	The station has no office but it's located at a 3 hours drive from the WIMEA office (Makerere)
Climatic Zone	Central zone
Grid power	The station has no grid power and only uses solar power. However Mr. Dhikusooka's house (about 10 meters from the station) has power.
Contact person	Mr. Dhikusooka Francis (0781436532 / 0759135331) and Mr. Ssebuufu Baanabakintu (0701844381/0777296638). They are the two observers at the station.
Space availability	There is sufficient space for deployment of the AWS.
Any support tools available	The station has no computer but other tools can be easily mobilised from Mubende town by Mr. Dhikusooka on demand.
Any caged stands for putting things like batteries?	None
Availability of casual labourers	Mr. Dhikusooka is willing to mobilise the labor in case of demand.

MBARARA SITE

Requirement	Field Finding
Signal strength	MTN signal strength was better , Airtel was fairly strong. Screen shots of the Network Cell Info app are provided in the folders MBARARA_SITE_RUHINDA and MBARARA_SITE_KASUMBA.
Possibility of other uplink methods (eg Ethernet)	No possibility.
Security	The station has a fence and there is a security guard (a mzee) and UNMA is planning to fence the land to prevent intruders from getting close to the station and the offices.
MET Personnel/Observers skills	The station has 2 observers, who have an office attendant and a security guard. The two observers have computer skills and the office has a computer as well. The didn't have any prior information about WIMEA-ICT. The Mbarara Met station is a synoptic station that requires them to collect data every 30 minutes but it was indicated that they would help WIMEA-ICT in case they were trained on how to monitor the AWS. It's easy to get people in Mbarara town who would

	help in the concrete works as long as there is facilitation. The attendant requested that in case WIMEA-ICT is planning to add any equipment to their office, they should add a new table as their might not be any table to put them.
Distance from meteorological office	The station is about 100m from the office. The office has power but no internet.
Status of stations with which to benchmark	It was reported that automatic weather stations are not normally monitored and information about their reliability can be got from UNMA directly.
What parameters existing station collects	Rainfall, wind speed, Dry Bulb, Wet bulb, wind direction, Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature, sunshine
How far the site is form the assembly point	About 100m considering the office as the assembly point.
Climatic Zone	South-western zone
Grid power	The MET office has power which can be extended to the station in case of need.
Contact person	Mr. Zaaake Joseph- Officer in Charge (0702226669/0776644999) Ms. Nakya Harriet Kasawuli-(Weather observer) (0776142999/0706142999)
Space availability	There is sufficient space for deployment of the AWS.
Any support tools available	The station has a computer. Other tools are not availability at the station but can be bought from Mbarara town.
Any caged stands for putting things like batteries?	None
Availability of casual labourers	They can be mobilised by Ms. Harriet Nankya from Mbarara.

NOTE: Mr. Waiswa indicated that from his experience, Airtel tends to support data connectivity in places with low signal strength, in comparison to MTN.

CHALLENGES.

- The phones we had at our disposal restricted our work; as Robert, who uses an iPhone could not get access to the iOS version of the application. He had to borrow from the people we found at the station so as to get the signal strength information.

- In addition to which, Kabonire's phone; dual sim is locked to only allow MTN to take up the slot for sim 1. This posed a problem when trying to attain the site map; as it was only readily available for the sim card in slot 1.
- Our Africell card failed to be read by the android phone we had available. The only other option was to adjust the phones lent to us, but the owners were not so open to the idea of swapping sim cards in their phones.
- Transportation from Mubende to Mbarara was quite difficult at that time, as Robert had to sleep there, due to failure to have a vehicle that travels instantly.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Sufficient time, for example a 48-hour notice, should be provided to the next team, to allow them collect all the necessary items needed to aid their site work.
- The team members going should always ensure they have all the necessary equipment, including phones, sim cards, power banks, among others, so as to ensure that the work they were sent out to do is achieved flawlessly.
- A vehicle should be provided to aid the swift movement of team members from one site to another.